

A CLUSTER APPROACH TO THE MANAGEMENT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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The direction of management of educational institutions

Abstract: The economic power of each country, the rise of the level of social and spiritual life is determined by the competitiveness of the educational system, the development of science. Therefore, in the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priority is to fundamentally improve the education sector, increase the quality of education, form a generation with intellectual potential, physical fitness, in-depth training of specific sciences, and training of qualified personnel for various sectors of the economy. were defined as tasks, and it was planned to create an educational system that could ultimately meet the requirements of today's era. This article discusses the cluster approach to preschool management.

Key words: Pre-school education, children, development, cluster management system, new approach, interactive methods.

In our country, the work towards building a democratic-legal, civil society of social development is being carried out step by step. The ultimate goal of all reforms is to create decent living conditions for citizens. It is for this reason that raising a spiritually perfect person is one of the most important tasks. Therefore, from the very first steps, the goal was to bring the national education system up to world standards. The implementation of such ambitious tasks could not be ensured without reforming the existing continuous education system in the country.

Today, huge reforms are being carried out in all parts of the education system in our country. Special attention is being paid to preschool education, which plays an important role in the future and development of our country. After all, this system

is the primary and most important link of society. It is confirmed by experts that 70% of all information that our children receive between the ages of 3 and 7 is absorbed, so the basis and foundation of education is preschool education and upbringing.

It is important to establish a cluster management system in preschool educational organizations. This system, which has been somewhat neglected and neglected for many years, has turned into a real place of education, thanks to the consistent reforms implemented under the leadership of the President. As a result of reforms in the field, the management mechanism in the preschool education system was fundamentally improved, the non-state educational service provision system was reformed, the secondary special, vocational education system was revised, the quality of training of highly educated specialists was improved.

In the process of cluster management of pre-school educational institutions, special importance is given to each system and stage. In this:

1. The selected games should match the age and individual characteristics of the students.
2. Each game should be pedagogically and psychologically based.
3. Not repeating the same games many times.
4. Paying attention to the educational, educational and developmental aspects of the game.
5. Encouraging children actively participating in the game.

Cluster education has important aspects in achieving the quality and efficiency of preschool education. In particular, rational and systematic analysis in order to organize children's daily activities in a meaningful and interesting way, to make effective use of free time, to identify their abilities and, accordingly, to creatively approach the process, to make the activities and resources for children meet the needs of children and society. intends to do.

In order to bring a cluster approach to the management of preschool educational organizations, taking into account advanced foreign experience, creating

conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children, improving the quality of preschool education, radically preparing children for school in preschool educational institutions improvement, introduction of modern educational programs and technologies widely used in the world practice into the educational process, improvement of the mechanism of training and professional development of pedagogic personnel in pre-school educational institutions were set.

In order for children to successfully study at school, it is not important to prepare them meaningfully in subjects. Because overloading it will reduce the desire to study. The main thing is to prepare him psychologically for school, to develop interest in learning, self-control skills, communicative and creative abilities, speech, memory, attention, and thinking.

In conclusion, the goal of the reforms implemented in our republic regarding the organization and management of education is aimed at achieving the single goal of educational subjects, forming a well-rounded person with a certain level of general education and professional training. In this process, it is possible to achieve high efficiency by applying cluster methods, management of pre-school educational institutions based on a new approach. Today, paying attention to education as a socio-pedagogical system developing on the basis of the general laws of society's development, education is a systematic object, legally, it requires a systematic approach to the management of all components. This requirement also applies to the educational process, which is implemented in all types of educational institutions.

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